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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

THE KNIGHTS OF THE SIBYL - GUERRINO THE WRETCH AND HIS FOREFATHERS: HUON OF BORDEAUX¹

1. A literary issue: the origin of "Guerrino the Wretch" and the "Paradise of Queen Sibyl"

A major problem in the investigation of the myth of the Apennine Sibyl is the literary origin of such works as "Guerrino the Wretch" by Andrea da Barberino and "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl" by Antoine de La Sale. Where did they get their tales from? Which earlier sources did they draw on?

Scholars are unanimous in saying that both authors put their hands in the world of chivalric romances and 'chansons de geste', usually set in the eighth and ninth century, the age of Emperor Charlemagne and the struggle between Christians and Moors.

Among the many epic poems pertaining to the Carolingian matter, with a preceding post we have highlighted the potential connections linking selected aspects of "Guerrino the Wretch" and "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl" with a specific chivalric poem which has not been adequately investigated with relation to the Apennine Sibyl and her legend: "Huon of Bordeaux", a thirteenth-century epic poem.

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(http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_LegendOrigin.asp)

Fig. 1 - Two chivalric romances, "Huon of Bordeaux" and "Guerrino the Wretch", and their connections to the legend of Mount Sibyl in Italy (in the background)

2. Huon's magical slamming doors

A brave knight sneaks into a forbidden, magical place to meet a being named Sibyl. One of the ordeals he must go through is a slamming barrier made of glistening metal, oscillating in a perpetual motion so as to prevent the faint-hearted from entering the fairy kingdom. Moreover, the valiant hero takes a journey to Rome to ask the Pope for his forgiving blessing.

Who's that knight? Is he Guerrino the Wretch, the main character of Andrea da Barberino's fifteenth-century famous romance? Or, maybe, is he one the unnamed knights in search of the Apennine Sibyl depicted by Antoine de La Sale in his fifteenth-century work "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl"?

Not at all. We have just been recounting the adventures of a different, earlier knight: Huon of Bordeaux.

Not many people know that some traits of Guerrino's deeds and adventures are seemingly drawn from a more ancient work: 'Huon of Bordeaux', an epic poem written in French and dating to the thirteenth century.

Just like 'Guerrino the Wretch', 'Huon of Bordeaux' has experienced a long-lasting success throughout the centuries, with lots of adaptations, translations, prose versions, and even dramatizations. One of the most famous of them is centered on a fairy character that is met for the very first time in this poem: the character is Auberon (Oberon), and the play he inspired was William Shakespeare's 'A Midsummer Night's Dream'.

But let's go back to our thirteenth-century poem: the main character is Huon, a valiant knight serving at the court of Charlemagne. A knight just like Guerrino. A knight living in the same age as 'The Wretch'.

The strange aspect in Huon's story - which was written more than one hundred fifty years before 'Guerrino the Wretch' and the 'Paradise of Queen Sibyl' were edited - is that a few details seem to have been used by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de La Sale in their accounts about the Apennine Sibyl.

But nobody has ever investigated these details in depth.

Let's take Huon's adventures following his departure from Paris: just like Guerrino, he leaves Europe and begins a journey to remote, outlandish regions lying beyond the Holy Land. There, he is told about Dunostre, a tower sitting beside the Red Sea: a magical tower, a sort of labyrinth with 300 windows and 25 rooms. A forbidden place. And the place is protected by something we have already heard of elsewhere:

«Two men are standing at the gate; they are made of bronze, each man holding a double scourge, all made of metal and terror-inspiring. They never stop striking and lashing to and from, throughout summer and winter. In truth I tell you that no small bird, as quick as it may be flurrying about, would never be able to get into the palace without being killed; it would not succeed in getting through» [in the original French text: «Et s'a deux hommes à l'entrer de l'ostel; Tout sont de keuvre et fait et compasé, Si tient cascuns un flaiel acouplé, Tout sont de fer, moult font à redouter. Tout adès batent et yver et esté, Et si vous di, par fine verité, Une aloete, que bien tost

set voler, Ne poroit mie ens el palais voler Que ne fust morte; ne poroit escaper»].

But isn't this magical barrier a close relative of the metal doors described by Antoine de La Sale as standing in the enchanted cave of the Apennine Sibyl in Italy? For a comparison, the following are de La Sale's words:

«within that cave, up to the metal doors, which slam ceaselessly day and night, opening wide and then shutting close again [...] in the cavern, there are two doors made of metal, slamming day and night without rest [...] These doors slam so savagely that everyone who wishes to enter is made aware that nobody can get through without being caught between them and crushed like a small fly. And that was what frightened them the more...» [in the original French text: «dedans ceste cave, jusques es portes de mettail, qui jour et nuyt et sans ceser battent, cloant et ouvrant [...] à l'endroit de la cave, sont les deux portes de metal, qui jour et nuyt batent sans cesser [...] Ces portes batent par telle maniere qu'il est proprement advis à celluy qui entrer y doit, qui'il n'y pourroit entrer sans estre entre deux cueilly et tout effroissé comme une mousche. Et ce fut la chose qui le plus espouvanta...»].

The revolving trap. A metal device protecting a fairy place. The ceaseless motion across days and nights and summers and winters. The frightful appearance of the whole contrivance. The small animals - birds or insects - used as an example of the crushing effect on the bold adventurers... Very similar. And very suspicious.

And this is not the sole coincidence.

3. Huon's journey to Rome

We saw that a specific episode in "Huon" appears to be very similar to one contained in "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl": revolving metal devices (scourges in the former, doors in the latter) which protect the access to a fairy world (the Dunostre tower in the former, the inner galleries of the Sibyl's cave in the latter).

Yet similarities are not over.

Fig. 2 - A drawing from the 1898 “Huon de Bourdeaux” precious edition by Gaston Paris, which shows Huon running his way through the bronze statues with their whipping scourges at Dunostre

Let's consider another famous episode found in "Guerrino the Wretch": as we already know, in Andrea da Barberino's chivalric romance the main character Guerrino rides to Rome so as to ask the Pope for forgiveness:

«He journeyed for many days heading to Rome. At the hotel he rested one day: then he went to St. Peter, and asked many people to have the chance to talk to the Holy Father [...] He kneeled down to the Pope's feet, he kissed them while he wept, as he cried for forgiveness». [in the original Italian text: «per molte giornate andò a Roma. A lo albergo se reposò uno giorno: poi andò a santo Pietro, e domandò a molti de parlare a lo santo padre [...] inzinocchiose in sina a li soi piedi, e basò li piedi sempre pianzendo, e cridando misericordia»].

The same happens to a German knight (possibly Tannhäuser) in de La Sale's text:

«And when he arrived to Rome, with no hesitation, as soon as he could, he went to St. Peter. Then he threw himself at the feet of a priest [...] 'Holy Father, said the knight [...] I come to you, the Vicar of Christ, to beg for forgiveness and mercy». [in the original French text: «Et quant il fut à Romme, sans plus attendre, tant qu'il peult, en l'eglise Saint Pierre s'en va. Lors se gecta aux pieds d'ung penancier [...] 'Pere Sainct, dist le chevalier [...] je viens à vous, Vicaire de Dieu, pour requerir pardon et mercy»].

But this episode, reported in the listed fifteenth-century works, is no original at all. Can you imagine who went to the Pope - some two hundred years earlier - looking for an absolution?

Of course, that's Huon:

«They came to the city of Rome. That night they were housed in a hotel; they were much attended and honored. And the subsequent day, when the day came [...] they went to the monastery of St. Peter. The Pope was celebrating a high mass; Huon listened to it as well as his companions. When it was over and the celebrations had ended, and the Pope came back from the monastery, Huon walked toward him [...] He confessed all his sins to him» [in the original French text: «il sont venu à Romme le chité. Cele nuit sont herbegié à l'ostel; Moul furent bien servi et honneré. Et l'endemain, quant il fu ajorné [...] au mostier Saint Piere en sont alé. Li apostoles faisoit messe canter; Hues l'escoute et se gent autretel. Quand dite fu et li mestiers finés, Et l'apostoles est du mostier tornés. Hues li est à son encontre alés [...] A lui s'est lues li enfes confesés»].

The slamming metal trap. The travel to the Pope. All that stuff seems to be suspiciously similar in these different literary works. And there is also a third, striking occurrence linking Huon with the sibilline myth.

In the magical tower of Dunostre, beyond the metal scourges ceaselessly lashing and whipping to prevent visitors from passing through, another encounter awaits the hero. Who is waiting for Huon in the enchanted castle? The answer is utterly surprising:

«The son of Sewin [Huon] from the town of Bordeaux, stroke three great blows on the golden basin [which stood beside the bronze guards]. A maiden in the castle listened to the resounding noise, her name was SEBILE, a most handsome lady; as soon as the golden basin resounded, she went by a window and saw Huon who was trying to get in». [in the original French text: «Li fieus Sewins, de Bordiax la cité, Sour le bacin qui fu f'or esmeré a fru trois cos par moult grande fierté. Une pucele ou u palais listé, Sebile ot nom, moult par ot de biauté; Si tost comme ot le bacin d'or sonner, A le fenestre s'en est venue ester, et voit Huon qui veut laiens entrer»].

The magical castle hides a young lady: a lady whose name is 'Sebile' - an ancient French spelling for the word 'Sibyl'.

Among all the possible names that might be selected for a maiden concealed within a magical tower, Huon is about to meet exactly 'Sibyl'. Just like Guerrino and de La Sale's German knight.

Just mere chance? Just another lucky strike connecting randomly "Huon of Bordeaux", "Guerrino the Wretch" and "The Paradise of Queen Sibyl"?

We don't think so. And it sounds strange to us that no professional scholars seem to have noticed the issue that stands out before our eyes. Here there is matter for much deeper study, involving a compared analysis of all three literary works.

However, that is exactly what "The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend" was born to: foster fresh attention and new research on a myth that still has much to deliver. And we will continue to propose new relevant reseach topics on a legend that continues to cast on men its timeless spell.

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